

GRDC Data Management and Analytics Core Framework

Strategic Elements

1. Capture valuable data

- Ensure GRDC's valuable data assets, and data important to the industry is identified and made findable
- Identify data and understand its meaning regardless of structure, origin or location
- Persist data in a structure and location that supports accessibility and reuse.

2. Make data accessible and actively share data and learnings

- Make sure maximum value can be derived from our data assets by ensuring they are findable and accessible for those who can use them to add-value to the grains industry
- Ensure data is packaged so it can be reused, shared and integrated.

3. Invest in analytics to create innovative insights and value

- Coupling data with analytics creates value through improved accuracy and prediction, as well as by revealing innovative new prospects.

4. Measure investment impact

- Further demonstrate the value of our investments to growers and the industry by finding efficient and sustainable ways to measure investment impact.

5. Ensure we have a workforce that has the necessary data and analytics skills and capacity

- Improve grains investment outcomes and foster innovation with a workforce who understand and can drive the power of data and analytics.

6. Apply governance for effective data usage

- Review and implement fit for purpose and efficient governance controls.

Guiding Principles

- GRDC invests in the creation of valuable data sets, and these are an asset
- GRDC identifies data, information and knowledge that has value in delivering on GRDC's Purpose and makes it findable
- A system of indexing and trusted data repositories will be GRDC's main approach for persistence of data
- National Infrastructure has a key role in capturing and persisting valuable data.

- Our data assets are accessible within legal and commercial constraints
- Data, information and knowledge that is generated through GRDC investment is created and managed with the knowledge that it will be shared and re-used
- We have appropriate access and sharing approaches for data we own, co-own, do not own.

- Extract additional value from our existing investment portfolio through the application of known, best practice analytics (including automation)
- Pursue the creation of additional value through the application of new and novel analytics
- Shift from descriptive to predictive analytics, which will lead to improved decision making and technology adoption
- Use national, international and commercial infrastructure.

- Measuring impact is critical to determining ROI for Australian grain growers
- Data will be managed with the intent of measuring investment impact
- Impact assessment will be used to define future investment in RD&E.

- The majority of the grains RD&E workforce must be equipped with a baseline set of skills in relation to data and analytics
- Create and support specialist capability and capacity in data analytics for grains RD&E
- The GRDC Capacity and Ability Core Framework provides GRDC's overall strategy for skills and capacity building within the industry.

- GRDC has a pivotal role in implementing data standards throughout our investment portfolio to ensure safe, consistent and effective use of data and analytics across projects and systems
- Investment decisions factor in data related risks and opportunities, including ethical, privacy, scientific and commercial considerations
- Requests for access to GRDC managed data are considered fairly, consistently and transparently.

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (FAIR)